

Scope & Topics

International journal of Web & Semantic Technology (IJWesT) is a quarterly open access peer-reviewed journal that provides excellent international forum for sharing knowledge and results in theory, methodology and applications of web & semantic technology. The growth of the World-Wide Web today is simply phenomenal. It continues to grow rapidly and new technologies, applications are being developed to support end users modern life. Semantic Technologies are designed to extend the capabilities of information on the Web and enterprise databases to be networked in meaningful ways. Semantic web is emerging as a core discipline in the field of Computer Science & Engineering from distributed computing, web engineering, databases, social networks, Multimedia, information systems, artificial intelligence, natural language processing, soft computing, and human-computer interaction. The adoption of standards like XML, Resource Description Framework and Web Ontology Language serve as foundation technologies to advancing the adoption of semantic technologies.

Topics of Interest

Authors are solicited to contribute to the conference by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the following areas, but are not limited to

- Semantic Query & Search
- Semantic Advertising and Marketing
- Linked Data, Taxonomies
- Collaboration and Social Networks
- Semantic Web and Web 2.0/AJAX, Web 3.0
- Semantic Case Studies
- Ontologies (Creation, Merging, Linking and Reconciliation)
- Semantic Integration Rules
- Data Integration and Mashups
- Unstructured Information
- Developing Semantic Applications
- Semantics for Enterprise Information Management (EIM)
- Knowledge Engineering and Management
- Semantic SOA (Service Oriented Architectures)
- Database Technologies for the Semantic Web
- Semantic Web for E-Business, Governance and E-Learning
- Semantic Brokering, Semantic Interoperability, Semantic Web Mining
- Semantic Web Services (Service Description, Discovery, Invocation, Composition)
- Semantic Web Inference Schemes
- Semantic Web Trust, Privacy, Security and Intellectual Property Rights
- Information Discovery and Retrieval in Semantic Web;
- Web Services Foundation, Architectures and Frameworks.
- Web Languages & Web Service Applications.
- Web Services-Driven Business Process Management.
- Collaborative Systems Techniques.
- Communication, Multimedia Applications Using Web Services
- Virtualization
- Federated Identity Management Systems
- Interoperability and Standards
- Social and Legal Aspect of Internet Computing
- Internet and Web-based Applications and Services

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through E-mail: ijwestjournal@airccse.org. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal.

Important Dates:

- **Submission Deadline : July 18, 2020**
- Author Notification : August 18, 2020
- Final Manuscript Due : August 26, 2020
- Publication Date : Determined by the Editor-in-Chief

Submission Link: <http://coneco2009.com/submissions/imagination/home.html>